
The Owen-Shapley spatial power index in three-dimensional space

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Abstract Inspired by Owen's (1971) previous work on the subject, Shapley (1977) introduced the Owen-Shapley spatial power index, which takes the ideological location of individuals into account, represented by vectors in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m , to measure their power. In this work we study the Owen-Shapley spatial power index in three-dimensional space. Peters and Zarzuelo (2017) carried out a study of this index for individuals are located in two-dimensional space, but pointed out the limitation of the two-dimensional feature. In this work focusing on three-dimensional space, we provide an explicit formula for spatial unanimity games, which makes it possible to calculate the Owen-Shapley spatial power index of any spatial game. We also give a characterization of the Owen-Shapley spatial power index employing two invariant positional axioms among others. Finally, we calculate this power index for the Basque Parliament, both in the two-dimensional and three-dimensional cases. We compare these positional indices against each other and against those that result when classical non-positional indices are considered, such as the Shapley-Shubik power index (1954) and the Banzhaf-normalized index (1965).

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1 Introduction

One of the most successful applications of cooperative game theory has been the ability to measure the power of agents in voting situations. These situations are represented through simple games, assigning the worth 1 to winning coalitions, and 0 to losers. Arguably, the most popular indices for measuring power are the classical Shapley-Shubik index (1954) and the Banzhaf index (1965). Both indices are based on whether an agent is pivotal or not, or equivalently, whether his or her presence is necessary to transform a losing coalition into a winning one. In the case of the Shapley-Shubik index, all possible orderings of players are considered. In any such ordering, one agent will play the pivotal role: when this agent joins the previous agents in the ordering, the coalition becomes a winning coalition. The Shapley-Shubik index assigns the probability of being pivotal to an agent when all

orderings are equally probable. The Banzhaf-normalized index also assigns the probability of an agent being pivotal but considers coalitions instead of orderings.

The Shapley-Shubik index does not take any implicit asymmetries between voters in a situation into account, such as ideological profiles, preferences on the issues at stake, or political outcomes. To remedy this shortcoming and inspired by an earlier paper of Owen (1971), Shapley (1977) proposed a spatial power index, known as the Owen-Shapley power index (see also Owen and Shapley, 1989). A spatial game is a simple game with a constellation of voter profiles, i.e., a set of vectors in the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m , representing the ideological locations of voters. One may think of the different dimensions as ideological considerations or criteria; consequently, each position represents the “ideal point” (of highest preference) in the space. Shapley (1977) justifies the use of the m -dimensional space \mathbb{R}^m as this “seems to leave us ample scope for capturing many kinds of political and ideological parameters without an excess of abstraction and generality”.

For Shapley (1977) an issue is a direction vector $r \in \mathbb{R}^m$, meaning that a player in position x is more in favor of r than a player in position y if $r \cdot x \leq r \cdot y$ (scalar product). Thus, every issue determines how players are ordered, from the most to the least enthusiastic, in which one of them plays the pivotal role. Similar to the Shapley-Shubik index, the Owen-Shapley value of a voter is the probability of being pivotal when all the issues are equiprobable.

Peters and Zarzuelo (2017) studied the Owen-Shapley spatial power index for two-dimensional space. They give a formula to calculate the index for unanimity games and provide an axiomatic characterization by employing a transfer axiom, a dummy axiom, anonymity and two invariant positional axioms. As pointed out above, Shapley’s aim with dimension m is to capture many kinds of parameters. He also writes in his work (1977) that “it is easy to conjure up situations in application where it is natural to have at least as many dimensions as players. For example, each person’s private welfare might require a separate coordinate of \mathbb{R}^m , making $m \geq n$.”

In this work we take a step towards exploring the Owen-Shapley spatial power index in more than two dimensions. More precisely, we study the index in three-dimensional space. Peters and Zarzuelo (2017) point out that their axioms could be extended for more dimensions, although it is not clear whether they would characterize this power index. We provide a formula to calculate the index for unanimity games. This formula makes it possible to calculate the Owen-Shapley spatial power index for any spatial simple game, since it is a linear combination of indices of unanimity games. We also prove that there are extensions of the five axioms used by Peters and Zarzuelo (2017) to characterize the three-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index, by using the following two key contributions. We employ one invariant positional axiom that requires the indices of the players not to change when the constellation is reflected with respect to a(any) plane, rather than with respect to a(any) line, as is the case for two-dimensional space. We generalize what we call a player’s scope with respect to a constellation, which is a real number that represents the position of players adjacent to the original one. Our second invariant positional axiom states that a player’s index will not change if the other players that approach him or her do not change the original player’s scope.

We also consider an application to the Basque Parliament. On the one hand, it serves as an illustration of the formulas obtained in this work. In addition, we observe that the Shapley-Shubik index and the Banzhaf normalized index do not reflect real power of a particular party in this parliament at all. By contrast, the Owen-Shapley spatial power index, in both two and three dimensions, gives a better measurement of the power of this party. Moreover, the three-dimensional model gives a measurement of power in this parliament that is closer to reality compared to the two-dimensional one: a powerless party becomes a party with some power when three dimensions are considered, and the rather high level of power of the governing party decreases.

Related work Owen's (1971) approach to defining his value is quite similar to Shapley's (1977), but differs in the definition of an issue (see Martin et al., 2014). For Owen (1971), an issue is a point in the Euclidean space (in fact in the hypersphere), and determines the ordering of the players depending on the order of increasing distances from the ideal points to the issue. Each of these ordering have a pivotal agent, and Owen proposes the probability of being pivotal as the power index of a player, provided that all the issues are equally likely. Note that a voter appears earlier in orders associated with issues closer to his or her "ideal point". Hence, one may think that individuals have preferences according to the simple Euclidean distance, i.e., in a comparison between any two issues, each voter prefers the issue closer to his or her ideal rather than the issue that is more distant from his or her ideal. It is worth noting that issues and ideal points are represented by m -dimensional vectors, both by Owen (1971) and Shapley (1977). However, in Owen's approach, issues and ideal points belong to the same space, whereas Shapley (1977) contends that they belong to different dual spaces and not to the same space. There are also other instances of spatial power indices. For example, Shenoy (1982) introduced a spatial power index that was an extension of the Banzhaf index when voters are represented by points in the m -dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m . Passarelli and Barr (2007) proposed a spatial power index in which agents and issues belong to the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m employing the multilinear extension approach introduced by Owen (1972) for cooperative games, which they then applied to the European Union (EU). Barr and Passarelli (2009) provided a family of spatial power indices that generalize the Owen-Shapley spatial power index when there is a probability distribution over issues, and analyzed the distribution of power in the Council of the EU. Alonso-Meijide et al. (2011) introduced a spatial power index that involves lengths of paths connecting players' positions, taking permutations of players into account, which they applied to the Catalan Parliament. Benati and Marzetti (2013) modelled voters' propensity to support an issue by means of a random utility function and obtained a family that included both the Shapley-Shubik index and the Owen-Shapley spatial power index. They applied their study to analyze the Council of the EU. Carreras and Albina-Puente (2015) introduced multinomial values that model different tendencies of agents.

Other studies have produced new findings on the Shapley-Shubik index and the Banzhaf index, as is the case of Freixas (2020), who employs simple multichoice games on his study, and Bernardi (2018), who provides an axiomatic characterization of the Banzhaf index when abstention is considered.

Structure of the paper The preliminaries are in Section 2, which is made up of four subsections: notation, spatial games, the Owen-Shapley spatial power index and the 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index for

unanimity games. Section 3 provides the 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index for unanimity games. Section 4 presents a characterization of the 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index. An application for the Basque Parliament can be found in Section 5.

Our paper ends with Section 6, with some concluding remarks. As far as future work is concerned, we think that a formula for the m -dimensional index of unanimity games can be obtained. This formula might also serve to answer the open question left by Owen and Shapley (1989) about whether the strong point and the center of power (which involves the Owen-Shapley index) coincide when there are more than two dimensions. Actually, they admitted that they "have been unable to find" a simple formula in order to prove it.

2 Preliminaries

Firstly, we present the basic concepts and the notation, some of it already used by Peters and Zarzuelo (2017).

2.1 Notation in \mathbb{R}^3

Given $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that $x \neq y$, the half-line which starts at x and passes through y is denoted by $[x, y, \rightarrow)$, and the segment with endpoints x and y by $[x, y]$. The perpendicular bisector plane of $[x, y]$ refers to the plane perpendicular to the line through x and y that passes through $\frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}y$. Given $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and a plane H in \mathbb{R}^3 such that $x \notin H$, x^H denotes the reflection of x with respect to H . Note that H is the perpendicular bisector plane of $[x, x^H]$. If $x \in H$, then $x^H = x$.

If, instead of a plane, H we consider a line ℓ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that $x \notin \ell$, x^ℓ will denote, analogously, the reflection of x with respect to ℓ , and ℓ will be a perpendicular bisector line of $[x, x^\ell]$. If $x \in \ell$, then $x^\ell = x$.

The projection of $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ on a line ℓ in \mathbb{R}^3 is denoted by \bar{x}^ℓ , that is, $\bar{x}^\ell = \frac{1}{2}x + \frac{1}{2}x^\ell$. Given that $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ and $y = (y_1, y_2, y_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $x \cdot y$ denotes the inner product of x and y , that is, $x \cdot y = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3$. If $x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\angle yxz$ refers to the angle between \vec{xy} and \vec{xz} (not greater than π). Given $X \subseteq \mathbb{R}^3$, $co(X)$ denotes the convex hull of X .

2.2 Spatial games

Let U be a set, the universe of players. A *coalition* is a finite nonempty subset of U . A *transferable utility (TU) game* is a pair (N, v) such that N is a coalition and $v: 2^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$, $v(\emptyset) = 0$. A *simple game* is a TU game (N, v) such that $v(S) \in \{0, 1\}$ for all $S \in 2^N$, $v(N) = 1$ and $v(S) \leq v(T)$ for all $S, T \in 2^N$ with $S \subseteq T$ (i.e., v is monotonic). Let (N, v) be a simple game. A coalition S is *winning* in (N, v) if $v(S) = 1$; otherwise S is *losing*. A *minimal winning coalition* is a winning coalition with no proper winning subcoalition. If $v(S) = 1$ and $v(S \setminus \{i\}) = 0$, it is said that player i is *pivotal* in S .

We denote the set of all TU games with set of players N by G^N and the subset of all simple games by \mathcal{S}^N .

A *constellation* for a set of players N is a vector $p = (p_i)_{i \in N} \in (\mathbb{R}^3)^N$ such that $p_i \neq p_j$ for all $i, j \in N$ with $i \neq j$. The set of all constellations for N is denoted by C^N . Given $p \in C^N$ and $S \subseteq N$, $p_S \in (\mathbb{R}^3)^S$ is defined by $(p_S)_i = p_i$ for all $i \in S$; and $co(p_S)$ denotes the convex hull of the set formed by the components of p_S .

Given a plane H in \mathbb{R}^3 and $p \in C^N$, we denote the constellation that is the reflection of p with respect to H by p^H , i.e., $p^H = (p_i^H)_{i \in N}$.

A *spatial game* with set of players N is a triple (N, v, p) such that $(N, v) \in \mathcal{S}^N$ and $p \in C^N$.

Player i is a *dummy* in (N, v, p) if $p_i \in co(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$ for every coalition S in which i is pivotal. This definition embodies the notion of a dummy in a nonspatial setting, in which, a dummy is an agent who is not pivotal in any coalition, and therefore, he or she satisfies this new definition. And in the spatial setting, if i is pivotal in a coalition S but $p_i \in co(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$, then player i will not be the last player in coalition S to consent, and therefore, i loses his or her pivoting power, and becomes a dummy.

A *spatial power index* on $A \subseteq \mathcal{S}^N$ is a function $\varphi : A \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ such that for all $(N, v, p) \in A$ it holds $\varphi_i(N, v, p) \geq 0$ for all $i \in N$ and $\sum_{i \in N} \varphi_i(N, v, p) = 1$.

Hence the power is not negative and it is assumed that total power equals 1.

2.3 The Owen-Shapley spatial power index

Let (N, v, p) be a spatial game and consider $r \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that $\|r\| = 1$, where $\|r\|$ denotes the Euclidean length of r . Each r represents a possible issue to be treated by the agents in N . At each r it is calculated the agent $i \in N$ who is pivotal in $\{j \in N \mid r \cdot p_j \leq r \cdot p_i\}$ and it is said that i is *pivotal at r* . Note that i is unique, except for a finite number of issues r . We assume that all issues are equally likely. The Owen-Shapley spatial power index of i , denoted $\Phi_i(N, v, p)$, is the probability that i is pivotal at an issue r .

A geometrical comment is in order. Given an issue r , consider a line ℓ with director vector r , and for each $j \in N$ the projection \bar{p}_j^ℓ on ℓ . We say that $j \in N$ precedes $k \in N$ on ℓ if \bar{p}_j^ℓ precedes \bar{p}_k^ℓ in the direction of r . Note that $i \in N$ is pivotal at r if and only if i is pivotal in the set of agents who precede him or her (including himself or herself) on ℓ .

If i is a dummy, then i is never pivotal at any issue r . Indeed, two cases are distinguished. If i is not pivotal in any coalition, it is obvious that i cannot be pivotal at any issue r . If i is pivotal in some S , since i is a dummy, then $p_i \in co(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$. Therefore, given any issue r and a line ℓ with director vector r , there will always be an agent j in S such that \bar{p}_i^ℓ precedes \bar{p}_j^ℓ . And therefore, i is not pivotal in the set of the agents who precede him or her (including i). Hence, i is not pivotal at r . Therefore, $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 0$.

The above definition and all the comments are valid for the 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index when constellation $p \in (\mathbb{R}^2)^N$ and issues $r \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

Fig. 1

2.4 The 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index for unanimity games

Vectors $r \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $\|r\| = 1$ represent issues and form the circle in \mathbb{R}^2 with radius 1. Let (N, v, p) be a spatial game. If ρ_i denotes the length of the arc or arcs for which i is pivotal at r , then

$$\Phi_i(N, v, p) = \frac{\rho_i}{2\pi},$$

since 2π is the length of the circle. The next presentation is similar to Peters and Zarzuelo (2017).

Let $v = u_S$, $\emptyset \neq S \subseteq N$, be the unanimity game on S , i.e., $u_S(T) = 1$ if $T \supseteq S$, and $u_S(T) = 0$ otherwise. If $i \notin S$, i is a dummy and, therefore, $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 0$.

If $|S| = 1$, then $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 1$ for $i \in S$.

Assume for the rest that $|S| > 1$. If $i \in S$ and $p_i \in \text{co}(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$, i is a dummy, and hence $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 0$. Let

$$S(p) = \{i \in S : p_i \notin \text{co}(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})\}, \quad (1)$$

i.e., the set of non-dummy players in (N, u_S, p) and let us calculate $\Phi_i(N, u_S, p)$ for $i \in S(p)$. Firstly, we make this observation. Let $i, j \in S$ and vector $r \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Suppose from now on that r starts at p_i and its length is 1. Let ℓ be the line through p_i and p_j (Figure 1), ℓ^\perp be the perpendicular line to ℓ through p_i and ℓ' be a line in the direction of r . Then, $\vec{p}_j^{\ell'}$ precedes $\vec{p}_i^{\ell'}$ in the direction of r if and only if r points to the half-space outside p_j with contour ℓ^\perp . Therefore, if $|S(p)| = 2$, then $\Phi_i(N, u_S, p) = 1/2$ for every $i \in S(p)$. Note that the spatial power index of i is determined by the issues r pointing to a half-space.

If $|S(p)| > 2$, for every $i \in S(p)$ there exists $j, k \in S(p) \setminus \{i\}$ such that p_j and p_k are adjacent vertices to p_i in $\text{co}(p_{S(p)})$ (Figure 2). It is proven in the following that the spatial power index of i is determined by the issues r pointing to the intersection of two half-spaces. Let ℓ (resp. m) be the line through p_i and p_j (resp. p_k), ℓ^\perp (resp. m^\perp) be the line perpendicular to ℓ (resp. m) through p_i , and ℓ' be a line in a direction of r . Then, $\vec{p}_k^{\ell'}$ precedes $\vec{p}_i^{\ell'}$

Fig. 2

in the direction of r for all $k \in S$ if and only if r is pointing outwards from $co(p_{S(p)})$ between ℓ^\perp and m^\perp . In other words, if r points to the intersection of the half-space outside p_j with contour ℓ^\perp and the half-space outside p_k with contour m^\perp . Since the length of the resulting arc is $\pi - \alpha_i$, then

$$\Phi_i(N, v, p) = \frac{\pi - \alpha_i}{2\pi}.$$

3 The 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index for unanimity games

Issues are represented by vectors $r \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that $\|r\| = 1$, which forms the sphere in \mathbb{R}^3 with radius 1, and area 4π . Let (N, v, p) be a spatial game. If ρ_i denotes the area of the portion of the surface of the sphere for which i is pivotal at r , then

$$\Phi_i(N, v, p) = \frac{\rho_i}{4\pi}.$$

Let $v = u_S$, $\emptyset \neq S \subseteq N$ be the unanimity game on S . As in the 2-dimensional case, if i is a dummy player in (N, u_S, p) then $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 0$, and, if $|S| = 1$, then $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = 1$ for $i \in S$. Assume for the rest that $|S| > 1$. Let us calculate $\Phi_i(N, u_S, p)$ for $i \in S(p)$, where $S(p)$ is defined as in (1), i.e., it refers to the set of non-dummy players in (N, u_S, p) . Now let $i, j \in S$, ℓ be the line through p_i and p_j (Figure 3), $Q^{i,j}$ be the plane through p_i with normal vector $\overrightarrow{p_i p_j}$ and ℓ' be a line in the direction of a vector r with length 1 starting also at p_i . Projecting p_i and p_j onto line ℓ' , point $\bar{p}_j^{\ell'}$ precedes point $\bar{p}_i^{\ell'}$ in the direction of r if, and only, if r points to the half-space outside p_j with contour $Q^{i,j}$.

Consequently, if $|S(p)| = 2$, then $\Phi_i(N, u_S, p) = 1/2$ for every $i \in S(p)$. Hence, as in the 2-dimensional case, the spatial power index of i is determined by the issues r pointing to a half-space.

If $|S(p)| = 3$, the following proves that the spatial power index of i is determined by the issues r pointing to the intersection of two half-spaces. Assume for simplicity that $S(p) = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Let $\alpha_0 = \angle p_1 p_0 p_2$ (Figure 4), $Q^{0,1}$ (resp. $Q^{0,2}$) be the plane through p_0 with normal vector $\overrightarrow{p_0 p_1}$ (resp. $\overrightarrow{p_0 p_2}$) and ℓ' be a line in a direction of r . Point $\bar{p}_k^{\ell'}$ precedes point $\bar{p}_0^{\ell'}$ in the direction of r for all $k \in S$, if, and only, if r points to the intersection of the

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

half-space outside p_1 with contour $Q^{0,1}$ and the half-space outside p_2 with contour $Q^{0,2}$. Note that those vectors r represent a lune with angle $\pi - \alpha_0$. Therefore, the area of this surface is $2(\pi - \alpha_0) \|r\|^2 = 2(\pi - \alpha_0)$ (see result 20 in Chapter I, Section II, J. Casey 1889), and hence

$$\Phi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{2(\pi - \alpha_0)}{4\pi} = \frac{\pi - \alpha_0}{2\pi}.$$

If $|S(p)| = 4$, we prove that the spatial power index of i is determined by the issues r pointing to the intersection of three half-spaces. Assume that $S(p) = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. Let $\alpha_0^{j,k} = \angle p_j p_0 p_k$, where $\{j, k\} \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $j < k$, $Q^{0,1}$ (resp. $Q^{0,2}$ and $Q^{0,3}$) (Figure 5) be the plane through p_0 with normal vector $\overrightarrow{p_0 p_1}$ (resp. $\overrightarrow{p_0 p_2}$ and $\overrightarrow{p_0 p_3}$) and ℓ' be

Fig. 5

a line in a direction of r . Point $\bar{p}_k^{\ell'}$ precedes point $\bar{p}_0^{\ell'}$ in the direction of r for all $k \in S$ if and only if r points to the intersection of the following three half-spaces: the half-space outside p_1 with contour $Q^{0,1}$, the half-space outside p_2 with contour $Q^{0,2}$ and the half-space outside p_3 with contour $Q^{0,3}$. Those vectors r represent a spherical triangle with angles $\pi - \alpha_0^{1,2}$, $\pi - \alpha_0^{1,3}$ and $\pi - \alpha_0^{2,3}$. Its area is (see result 21, Gerard's Theorem in Chapter I, Section II, J. Casey 1889)

$$\left((\pi - \alpha_0^{1,2}) + (\pi - \alpha_0^{1,3}) + (\pi - \alpha_0^{2,3}) - \pi \right) \|r\|^2 = 2\pi - (\alpha_0^{1,2} + \alpha_0^{1,3} + \alpha_0^{2,3}),$$

and, therefore,

$$\Phi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{2\pi - (\alpha_0^{1,2} + \alpha_0^{1,3} + \alpha_0^{2,3})}{4\pi}.$$

In general, the surface for which $i \in S(p)$ is pivotal is a spherical polygon of t sides, where t is the number of vertices in $co(p_{S(p)})$ that are also adjacent to p_i . This spherical polygon results from the intersection of t half-spaces and the sphere of radius 1 and origin p_i . The angles of this spherical polygon are $\pi - \alpha_i^{j,k}$, where $\alpha_i^{j,k} = \angle p_j p_i p_k$ and p_j, p_k are adjacent vertices in $co(p_{S(p)})$ that are adjacent to p_i . Let Λ_i be the set formed by $\alpha_i^{j,k}$. The area of this spherical polygon is (see Corolary 2 of Gerard's Theorem, J. Casey 1889)

$$(2 - m) \pi + \sum_{\alpha_i^{j,k} \in \Lambda_i} (\pi - \alpha_i^{j,k}).$$

And therefore,

$$\Phi_i(N, u_S, p) = \frac{(2 - m) \pi + \sum_{\alpha_i^{j,k} \in \Lambda_i} (\pi - \alpha_i^{j,k})}{4\pi} = \frac{2\pi - \sum_{\alpha_i^{j,k} \in \Lambda_i} \alpha_i^{j,k}}{4\pi}. \quad (2)$$

4 A characterization for the 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index

Peters and Zarzuelo (2017) characterize the 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index by means of five axioms. In this section the Owen-Shapley spatial power index is characterized by adapting these axioms to the 3-dimensional case.

The first axiom is equivalent to Dubey's (1975) transfer axiom, as remarked in Dubey et al. (2005).

Equal Power Change (EPC) For all set of players N , all $p \in C^N$, and all $v, v', w, w' \in \mathcal{S}^N$, if $v - v' = w - w' \geq 0$, then

$$\varphi(N, v, p) - \varphi(N, v', p) = \varphi(N, w, p) - \varphi(N, w', p).$$

Hence, if the same winning coalitions are needed to go from v to v' as those to go from w to w' , then the change in power for those spatial games is the same.

For the second axiom a new definition is needed. If $(N, v) \in \mathcal{S}^N$ is such that $|N| \geq 2$ and $i \in N$, then game $(N \setminus \{i\}, v_{-i}) \in \mathcal{S}^{N \setminus \{i\}}$ is defined by

$$v_{-i}(S) = \begin{cases} v(S \cup \{i\}) & \text{if } \emptyset \neq S \subseteq N \setminus \{i\}, \\ 0 & \text{if } S = \emptyset. \end{cases}$$

We can think that $(N \setminus \{i\}, v_{-i})$ results when player i leaves the game and leaves his or her consent, since any winning coalition in (N, v) containing i will also win in $(N \setminus \{i\}, v_{-i})$, after player i leaves the game.

Dummy Property (DP) For every spatial game (N, v, p) and every dummy i in (N, v, p) ,

$$\varphi_j(N, v, p) = \varphi_j(N \setminus \{i\}, v_{-i}, p_{N \setminus \{i\}})$$

for all $j \in N \setminus \{i\}$.

This axiom requires the power not to change if a dummy player leaves the game. Hence, since the addition of indices in a spatial game is 1, it also implies that the power of a dummy player is zero.

An anonymity axiom is also required: power does not depend on the players' names. Given a spatial game (N, v, p) and an injective function $\sigma : N \rightarrow U$, the spatial game $(\sigma(N), \sigma v, \sigma p)$ is defined by $\sigma v(\sigma(S)) = v(S)$ for every $S \subseteq N$ and $(\sigma p)_{\sigma(i)} = p_i$ for every $i \in N$.

Anonymity (AN) For every spatial game (N, v, p) and every injective function $\sigma : N \rightarrow U$,

$$\varphi_{\sigma(i)}(\sigma(N), \sigma v, \sigma p) = \varphi_i(N, v, p),$$

for every $i \in N$.

The fourth axiom tells us that it does not matter where the constellation lies; only the relative positions between players. It is formalized by means of reflections of constellations.

Reflection Invariance (RI) For every spatial game (N, v, p) and every plane Q in \mathbb{R}^3 ,

$$\varphi(N, v, p) = \varphi(N, v, p^Q).$$

If we compare this axiom with the Reflection Invariance axiom for \mathbb{R}^2 , the positions are reflected with respect to planes instead of lines.

Here we give a new definition for the latter: the scope. Given $i \in N$ and $p \in C^N$ such that p_i is a vertex in $co(p_N)$, we denote the set formed by the players j in N such that p_j are the vertices in $co(p_N)$ adjacent to p_i by $Ad(i, p)$. We write $Ad(i, p) = \{i_0, \dots, i_k\}$, where p_{i_ℓ} is adjacent to $p_{i_{\ell'}}$ when $\ell' = \ell + 1$, and p_{i_k} is adjacent to p_{i_0} . The scope of i with respect to p is defined as follows:

$$scope(i, p) = \angle p_{i_0} p_i p_{i_k} + \sum_{\ell=0}^{k-1} \angle p_{i_\ell} p_i p_{i_{\ell+1}}$$

Thus, it is composed of the angles that determine players in $Ad(i, p)$ with respect to i . This number can be viewed as the overall position of players in $Ad(i, p)$ with respect to i .

We also include the concept of p-type coalition introduced by Kalai and Samet (1987): S is a p-type coalition, if it holds $v(R \cup T) = v(R)$ for each $T \subseteq S$ and each $R \subseteq N \setminus S$. That is, all proper sub-coalitions of S are powerless, since they do not change the worth of any coalitions outside S . Coalition S can be seen as an individual.

In the following axiom, players in $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\}$ form a p-type coalition. The axiom requires the power of i not to change when players in $Ad(i, p)$ move their location without changing their overall position (the scope) with respect to i .

Three-dimensional Positional Invariance (3DPI) For all player sets N and $i \in N$, if p_i (resp. p'_i) is a vertex in $co(p_N)$ (resp. $co(p'_N)$), $p, p' \in C^N$ satisfy $Ad(i, p) = Ad(i, p')$, players in $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\}$ form a p-type coalition in $(N, v) \in \mathcal{S}^N$, $p'_j \in [p_i, p_j, \rightarrow)$ for every $j \in N \setminus Ad(i, p)$ and

$$scope(i, p) = scope(i, p'),$$

then

$$\varphi_i(N, v, p) = \varphi_i(N, v, p').$$

Also note that any player j not adjacent to i is allowed to move towards the location of i along the straight line that joins the location of j with the location of i . We can see this movement as an invariant movement, since the relative position of the players does not change with respect to issues.

If we compare this axiom with the PI in \mathbb{R}^2 employed by Peters and Zarzuelo (2017), note that in the two-dimensional case, $Ad(i, p)$ would only be formed by two players j and k , and therefore, $scope(i, p) = \angle p_j p_i p_k$. Axiom 3DPI would say that, if this angle does not change, then the power of i does not change either. Looking at

PI in \mathbb{R}^2 , PI requires the power of i not to change if j and k move towards or out to i in a straight line. Hence, it also requires $\angle p_j p_i p_k$, i.e., the scope, not to change.

Theorem 1 *The Owen-Shapley spatial power index is the unique spatial power index on \mathcal{S}^N that satisfies EPC, DP, AN, RI and 3DPI.*

We prove this characterization in a series of steps. Firstly, we have Lemma 1 that is followed by Lemma 2.3 in Einy (1987). See also Einy and Haimanko (2011). It reduces the spatial power index of a game to spatial power indices of unanimity games if the power index satisfies EPC. It will be employed for uniqueness and to prove that the Owen-Shapley spatial power index satisfies the axiomatic characterization (Lemma 2).

Lemma 1 *Let φ be a spatial power index that satisfies EPC and (N, v, p) be a spatial game such that S_1, \dots, S_k are the minimal winning coalitions of (N, v) . Then,*

$$\varphi(N, v, p) = \sum_{\emptyset \neq I \subseteq \{1, \dots, k\}} (-1)^{|I|+1} \varphi(N, u_{\cup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}}, p).$$

Lemma 2 *The Owen-Shapley spatial power index satisfies EPC, DP, AN, RI and 3DPI.*

Proof Axioms EPC, DP and AN are satisfied, as shown by Peters and Zarzuelo (2017). As for RI, consider a spatial game (N, v, p) , a plane Q in \mathbb{R}^3 and $i \in N$. Note that i is pivotal at an issue r if and only if i is pivotal at r^Q with respect to (N, v, p^Q) . Since all the issues are equally likely, then $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = \Phi_i(N, v, p^Q)$.

For 3DPI, consider a spatial game (N, v, p) with minimal winning coalitions S_1, \dots, S_k , $i \in N$, $p, p' \in C^N$ such that p_i (resp. p'_i) is a vertex of $co(p_N)$ (resp. $co(p'_N)$), $Ad(i, p) = Ad(i, p')$, $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\}$ is a p-type coalition in $(N, v) \in \mathcal{S}^N$, $p'_j \in [p_j, p_j, \rightarrow)$ for all $j \in N \setminus Ad(i, p)$ and $scope(i, p) = scope(i, p')$.

Since $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\}$ is a p-type coalition, then $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\} \subseteq N \setminus S_{k'}$ or $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\} \subseteq S_{k'}$ for all minimal coalition $S_{k'}$ of (N, v, p) , and, therefore,

$$Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\} \subseteq N \setminus \left(\bigcup_{k' \in I} S_{k'} \right) \text{ or } Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\} \subseteq \bigcup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}$$

for all $\emptyset \neq I \subseteq \{1, \dots, k\}$. In the first case,

$$\Phi_i(N, u_{\cup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}}, p) = 0 = \Phi_i(N, u_{\cup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}}, p').$$

In the second case, taking into account that $Ad(i, p) \cup \{i\} \in co(p_N)$, by (2),

$$\Phi_i(N, u_{\cup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}}, p) = \frac{2\pi - scope(i, p)}{4\pi} = \Phi_i(N, u_{\cup_{k' \in I} S_{k'}}, p').$$

Therefore, by Lemma 1, we get $\Phi_i(N, v, p) = \Phi_i(N, v, p')$.

Q.E.D.

For uniqueness, by Lemma 1, we focus on unanimity games u_S . We denote a power index that satisfies EPC, DP, AN, RI and 3DPI by φ , and we prove Lemmas 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7, and Propositions 1 and 2. A guideline is provided for them to make overall reading clearer.

In Lemma 3 a player is considered with more than three adjacent players in $co(p_S)$, i.e., with more than three adjacent non-dummy players. It can be proven that his or her power index only depends on the power index of players with only three adjacent non-dummy players. This result makes it possible for the other lemmas and propositions to consider such kinds of players.

In Lemma 4, we consider the case in which the three non-dummy adjacent players form right angles. In Proposition 1, we determine the index when the three non-dummy adjacent players form two right. And in Proposition 2 we determine the index when the three adjacent non-dummy players are in any location.

The result from Lemma 5 is key to getting Lemma 6, which, together with Lemma 7, makes it possible to satisfy Proposition 1. The results and proofs of Lemmas 5 and 7 are illustrated by means of figures, and Lemma 6 can be seen as an intermediate statement in between Lemma 4 and Proposition 1, since Lemma 6 expands the case of Lemma 4 to a dense subset of the cases in Proposition 1. Proof of Theorem 1, which is given at the end of this section, takes Lemma 3 and Proposition 2 into account. Proofs for lemmas 5 and 7 are given in the appendix.

Lemma 3 *Let (N, u_S, p) and $i \in S(p)$ such that $|Ad(i, p_S)| > 3$. Then, there exists $T \subseteq S$ and $p' \in C^T$ such that $i \in T(p') = \left\{ j \in T : p'_i \notin co\left(p'_{T \setminus \{i\}}\right) \right\}$,*

$$\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = 1 - \sum_{j \in Ad(i, p')} \varphi_j(T, u_T, p'),$$

and $|Ad(j, p')| = 3$ for all $j \in T \setminus \{i\}$.

Proof Let (N, u_S, p) and $i \in S(p)$ such that $|Ad(i, p)| > 3$. By DP,

$$\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = \varphi_i(S(p), u_{S(p)}, p_{S(p)}).$$

We approach the points p_j , $j \in S(p) \setminus \{i\}$, to p_i in $[p_i, p_j, \rightarrow)$ in such a way that all of them belong to the same plane. Let q be the resulting constellation (Figure 6).

By 3DPI,

$$\varphi_i(S(p), u_{S(p)}, p_{S(p)}) = \varphi_i(S(p), u_{S(p)}, q).$$

Since players in $S(p) \setminus (Ad(i, p_S) \cup \{i\})$ are dummy players in $(S(p), u_{S(p)}, q)$, if we consider $T = Ad(i, p_S) \cup \{i\}$ and the constellation $p' = q_T$, by DP,

$$\varphi_i(S(p), u_{S(p)}, q) = \varphi_i(T, u_T, p').$$

Fig. 6 In this figure $i = 0$, $S(p) = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$, $Ad(0, p) = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, and $q_0 = p_0$, $q_1 = p_1$, $q_3 = p_3$ and $q_4 = p_4$.

Fig. 7 In this figure $q_0 = p_0$, $q_1 = p_1$, $q_2 = p_2$ and $q_3 = p_3$.

Furthermore, $|Ad(j, p')| = 3$ for all $j \in T(p') \setminus \{i\}$. Taking into account that φ is a spatial index,

$$\varphi_i(T, u_T, p') = 1 - \sum_{j \in Ad(i, p')} \Phi_j(T, u_T, p'),$$

and the required equality is obtained. Q.E.D.

Lemma 4 Let (N, u_S, p) be such that $0 \in S(p)$, $Ad(0, p_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and

$$(\angle p_1 p_0 p_2, \angle p_2 p_0 p_3, \angle p_1 p_0 p_3) = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right).$$

Then, $\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{1}{8}$.

Proof By DP and 3DPI,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \varphi_0(\{0, 1, 2, 3\}, u_{\{0,1,2,3\}}, p_{\{0,1,2,3\}}).$$

Let $T = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$, and $q \in C^T$ such that $q_{\{0,1,2,3\}} = p_{\{0,1,2,3\}}$ and $co(q)$ is a prism (Figure 7). DP and 3DPI imply

Fig. 8

$$\varphi_0(\{0, 1, 2, 3\}, u_{\{0,1,2,3\}}, P_{\{0,1,2,3\}}) = \varphi_0(T, u_T, q).$$

And by RI, AN and the definition of a spatial index,

$$\varphi_0(T, u_T, q) = \frac{1}{8}.$$

Therefore, the result is obtained.

Q.E.D.

Lemma 5 Let $a, b, c, d, e \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that a, c, d, e belong to the same plane in \mathbb{R}^3 , $\angle dac < \pi$, $e \in [d, c]$ and $\angle bad = \angle bac = \pi/2$ (Figure 8); and $p, q, s \in \mathbb{C}^N$, $(N, u_S) \in \mathcal{S}^N$ such that $0 \in S(p) \cap S(q) \cap S(s)$, $Ad(0, p_S) = Ad(0, q_S) = Ad(0, s_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $(p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3) = (a, c, d, b)$, $(q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3) = (a, e, d, b)$ and $(s_0, s_1, s_2, s_3) = (a, c, e, b)$. Then,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \varphi_0(N, u_S, q) + \varphi_0(N, u_S, s) - \frac{1}{4}.$$

If, moreover, $\angle cae = \angle dae$, then

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = 2\varphi_0(N, u_S, q) - \frac{1}{4}.$$

Lemma 6 Let (N, u_S, p) be such that $0 \in S(p)$, $Ad(0, p_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and

$$(\angle p_1 p_0 p_2, \angle p_2 p_0 p_3, \angle p_1 p_0 p_3) = \left(\frac{m}{2^h} \pi, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right),$$

where $m, h \in \mathbb{N}$ and $m < 2^h$. Then,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{1}{4} - \frac{m}{2^{h+2}}.$$

Proof We will now use induction on m to prove this.

Let $m = 1$. We prove this step by induction on h . When $h = 1$, Lemma 4 implies that $\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = 1/8$, and therefore the statement is true.

Suppose that the equality holds for h and let us prove it for $h + 1$. By Lemma 5 and induction

$$\frac{1}{4} - \frac{m}{2^{h+2}} = 2\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) - \frac{1}{4}.$$

And hence,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{1}{4} - \frac{m}{2^{h+3}}.$$

Suppose that the result is true for m and let us prove it for $m + 1$ and h such that $m + 1 < 2^h$. Taking Lemma 5 into account,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \varphi_0(N, u_S, q) + \varphi_0(N, u_S, s) - \frac{1}{4},$$

where $q, s \in C^N$ satisfy $Ad(0, q_S) = Ad(0, s_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\angle q_1 q_0 q_2, \angle q_2 q_0 q_3, \angle q_1 q_0 q_3) &= \left(\frac{m}{2^h} \pi, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right) \text{ and} \\ (\angle s_1 s_0 s_2, \angle s_2 s_0 s_3, \angle s_1 s_0 s_3) &= \left(\frac{\pi}{2^h}, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

By induction,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{m}{2^{h+2}} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{2^{h+2}} \right) - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{1}{4} - \frac{m+1}{2^{h+2}},$$

and the result is obtained. Q.E.D.

Lemma 7 Let $a, b, c, d, e \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that a, c, d, e belong to the same plane in \mathbb{R}^3 , $\angle dac < \pi$, $e \in [d, c]$ and $\angle bad = \angle bac = \pi/2$ (Figure 8); and $p, q \in C^N$, $(N, u_S) \in \mathcal{S}^N$ such that $0 \in S(p) \cap S(q)$, $Ad(0, p_S) = Ad(0, q_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$, $(p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3) = (a, c, d, b)$ and $(q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3) = (a, e, d, b)$. Then,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) \leq \varphi_0(N, u_S, q).$$

Proposition 1 Let (N, u_S, p) be such that $0 \in S(p)$, $Ad(0, p_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$ and

$$(\angle p_1 p_0 p_2, \angle p_2 p_0 p_3, \angle p_1 p_0 p_3) = \left(\alpha, \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{\pi}{2} \right),$$

where $\alpha \in (0, \pi)$. Then,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{\pi - \alpha}{4\pi}.$$

Proof By Lemma 6, $\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = (\pi - \alpha)/4\pi$ when $\alpha = m\pi/2^h$, where $m, h \in \mathbb{N}$ and $m < 2^h$. Therefore, the statement of the Proposition is true for a dense subset of $(0, \pi)$. Since function $\alpha \mapsto (\pi - \alpha)/4\pi$ is a non-increasing continuous function on this subset, Lemma 7 implies the required equality. Q.E.D.

Proposition 2 Let (N, u_S, p) such that $0 \in S(p)$ and $Ad(0, p_S) = \{1, 2, 3\}$. Then,

$$\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) = \frac{2\pi - (\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3)}{4\pi}.$$

Fig. 9

Proof Proposition 1 gives the statement when two angles are equal to $\pi/2$. We prove the rest of the cases in several steps. Let $\tilde{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. By DP and 3DPI we have to prove

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \frac{2\pi - (\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3)}{4\pi}.$$

Case 1: $\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 > \pi$. Let $q \in C^{\tilde{N}}$ such that

$$(\angle q_1 q_0 q_2, \angle q_2 q_0 q_3, \angle q_1 q_0 q_3) = (\pi/2, \pi/2, \alpha),$$

where $\alpha = \angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 - \pi$ (notice that $\alpha < \pi$ since $\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 < 2\pi$).

Then,

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q) = \frac{2\pi - (\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2} + \alpha)}{4\pi},$$

where the first equality holds by 3DPI and the second one by Proposition 1. Therefore, the required equality is obtained.

Case 2: $\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 = \pi$. By 3DPI, we can suppose without loss of generality that $(\angle p_1 p_0 p_2, \angle p_2 p_0 p_3, \angle p_1 p_0 p_3) = (\pi/3, \pi/3, \pi/3)$ and that the distances from p_0 to p_1 , from p_0 to p_2 and from p_0 to p_3 are equal (approaching p_1 , p_2 and p_3 towards p_0). Since all angles in $co(p_{\tilde{N}})$ are equal to $\pi/3$, RI and AN (Figure 9) imply

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \varphi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}})$$

for $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$, and since φ is an index, $\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = 1/4$, and the result is obtained.

Case 3:

$$\pi/3 < \angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 < \pi. \quad (3)$$

Fig. 10

Firstly, a preliminary result is proved. Let $\alpha \in (\pi/3, \pi)$ and $q \in C^{\tilde{N}}$ (Figure 10) such that

$$(\angle q_1 q_0 q_2, \angle q_2 q_0 q_3, \angle q_1 q_0 q_3) = (\pi/3, \pi/3, \alpha),$$

$$(\angle q_0 q_1 q_2, \angle q_0 q_1 q_3, \angle q_2 q_1 q_3) = (\pi/3, \pi/3, \alpha),$$

$$(\angle q_0 q_2 q_1, \angle q_0 q_2 q_3, \angle q_1 q_2 q_3) = (\pi/3, (\pi - \alpha)/2, (\pi - \alpha)/2),$$

and

$$(\angle q_0 q_3 q_1, \angle q_0 q_3 q_2, \angle q_1 q_3 q_2) = (\pi/3, (\pi - \alpha)/2, (\pi - \alpha)/2).$$

Since we are in Case 1 with q , then

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q) = \frac{2\pi - (\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{3} + \alpha)}{4\pi}. \quad (4)$$

Applying RI and AN, and taking the fact that φ is a power index into account, then

$$2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q) + 2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q) = 1,$$

And by (4),

$$\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(2\pi - \left(\frac{\pi}{3} + \frac{\pi}{3} + \alpha \right) \right) \right) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(\frac{2\pi}{3} + \alpha \right). \quad (5)$$

Now let $q' \in C^{\tilde{N}}$ such that $q'_0 = p_0$ and

$$(\angle q'_1 q'_0 q'_2, \angle q'_2 q'_0 q'_3, \angle q'_1 q'_0 q'_3) = (\pi/3, (\pi - \alpha')/2, (\pi - \alpha')/2),$$

where $\alpha' = 4\pi/3 - \angle p_1 p_0 p_2 - \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 - \angle p_1 p_0 p_3$. By (3), we have $\pi/3 < \alpha' < \pi$. By 3DPI,

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q'),$$

and by AN and (5),

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, q') = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left(\frac{2\pi}{3} + \alpha' \right) = \frac{2\pi - (\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3)}{4\pi},$$

and this case is proved.

Case 4: $\angle p_1 p_0 p_2 + \angle p_2 p_0 p_3 + \angle p_1 p_0 p_3 \leq \pi/3$. Then, $\angle p_j p_0 p_k \leq \pi/6$ for all $j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ such that $j < k$. Let us fix $j, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ such that $j < k$, and let $k' \in \tilde{N} \setminus \{0, j, k\}$. Since

$$\angle p_j p_0 p_k + \angle p_0 p_j p_k + \angle p_0 p_k p_j = \pi,$$

then $\angle p_0 p_j p_k + \angle p_0 p_k p_j \geq 5\pi/6$. Moreover, by 3DPI (approaching conveniently in straight line j, k and k' towards 0), we can suppose that $\angle p_0 p_j p_k \leq \pi/2$ and $\angle p_0 p_k p_j \leq \pi/2$. Hence, $\angle p_0 p_k p_j \geq \pi/3$ and $\angle p_0 p_j p_k \geq \pi/3$. We can reason in the same way for each pair $j', k' \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ such that $j' < k'$, and therefore, $\angle p_0 p_{k'} p_{j'} \geq \pi/3$ and $\angle p_0 p_{j'} p_{k'} \geq \pi/3$. Consequently, players 1, 2 and 3 are in Case 1, Case 2 or Case 3 with respect to p . Therefore, by AN, $\varphi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \Phi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}})$ when $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Since φ is a power index,

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^3 \Phi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}) = \Phi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, p_{\tilde{N}}),$$

and this proof is complete. Q.E.D.

Proof of Theorem 1. We have proved in Lemma 1 that Φ satisfies the axioms in the statement.

For uniqueness, let (N, u_S, p) and $i \in S$. If $i \notin S$, then i is a dummy player and hence $\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = 0$. If $|S| = 1$, by definition of a spatial power index, $\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = 1$ for $i \in S$.

Assume for the rest that $|S| > 1$. If $i \in S$ and $p_i \in co(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$, i is a dummy player, and consequently $\varphi_i(N, v, p) = 0$. Let us prove that the power index is determined for players in $S(p)$.

If $|S(p)| = 2$, RI implies $\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = 1/2$ for every $i \in S(p)$. If $|S(p)| = 3$, in fact players are located in \mathbb{R}^2 and the 3-dimensional axioms EPC, DP, AN, RI and 3DPI imply the 2-dimensional axioms. Therefore, for every $i \in S(p)$, $\varphi_i(N, u_S, p)$ coincides with the 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index.

If $|S(p)| > 3$, by Lemma 3 and Proposition 2, $\varphi_i(N, u_S, p) = \Phi_i(N, u_S, p)$ for every $i \in S(p)$ and the proof is complete. Q.E.D.

5 An application

In this section we consider the Basque Parliament elected in 2016. There are 5 parties: Eusko Alderdi Jeltzalea/Partido Nacionalista Vasco (EAJ/PNV), Euskal Herria Bildu (EHB), Elkarrekin Podemos (EP), Partido Socialista de Euskadi (PSE) and Partido Popular (PP). There are 75 seats, therefore, 38 seats are needed for a majority. They are distributed as follows.

EAJ/PNV (1)	EHB (2)	EP (3)	PSE (4)	PP (5)
28	18	11	9	9

The classical non-positional Shapley-Shubik power index and Banzhaf normalized index of this majority game v are given below.

*	EAJ/PNV (1)	EHB (2)	EP (3)	PSE (4)	PP (5)
<i>Sh</i>	0.4	0.23	0.23	0.07	0.07
<i>Bz</i>	0.38	0.23	0.23	0.08	0.08

Looking at these indices, PSE and PP have the same power (in both cases), since they have the same number of seats. However, this does not reflect the real power that PSE has in the Basque Parliament. In fact, the Basque Government, whose president is elected by this parliament, is a coalition government composed of EAJ/PNV and PSE. The former party has the highest index, which reflects the fact that the head of the government and majority of its members belong to EAJ/PNV, but the low index for the PSE, which is the same as the index for PP, does not reflect the PSE's real power. In fact, PSE has three counselors out of eleven that make up the Basque Government. These results lead us to explore spatial power indices to measure power, for which political affinities of parties will be taken into account.

If we turn to the Owen-Shapley spatial power index, first we have to position parties according to some variables. Those variables can be provided from the Euskobarometer (2016), a political research magazine from the University of the Basque Country that produces opinion polls from voters. The political parties are represented on the following axes: left-right, Basque nationalist-Spanish nationalist, and approval-disapproval of political parties' behavior.

*	EAJ/PNV (1)	EHB (2)	EP (3)	PSE (4)	PP (5)
Left-right	5.4	2.2	3	4.6	7.7
Basque nat-Span.	2.9	1.6	5.1	6.8	8.3
App-disapp	4.8	2.3	1.7	0.5	0.2

For example, we can calculate, both the Owen-Shapley spatial power index w.r.t. the first two variables and w.r.t. the three variables. Let $N = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and p be the constellation according to the left-right and Basque nationalist-Spanish nationalist axes (Figure 11). Taking into account that the minimal winning coalitions of (N, v) are $\{1, 3\}$, $\{1, 2\}$, $\{1, 4, 5\}$, $\{2, 3, 5\}$ and $\{2, 3, 4\}$, by Lemma 1, the Owen-Shapley spatial power index of this majority spatial game can be split into indices of unanimity games (N, u_S, p) .

Fig. 11

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi_i(N, v, p) &= \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,3\}}, p) + \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,2\}}, p) - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,2,3\}}, p) \\
&\quad + \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,4,5\}}, p) + \Phi_i(N, u_{\{2,3,5\}}, p) + \Phi_i(N, u_{\{2,3,4\}}, p) \\
&\quad - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,2,3,4\}}, p) - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,2,4,5\}}, p) - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{2,3,4,5\}}, p) \\
&\quad - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,2,3,5\}}, p) - \Phi_i(N, u_{\{1,3,4,5\}}, p) + 2\Phi_i(N, u_N, p),
\end{aligned}$$

for all $i \in N$. Notice that in all cases the equality $S(p) = S$ holds, where $S(p)$ is defined as in (1). Hence, all players in S are non-dummy players in (N, u_S, p) . As an illustration, let us calculate some of those indices. For example, if $i = 1$, formula in Subsection 2.4 (Figure 2) implies

$$\Phi_1(N, u_{\{1,2,3\}}, p) = \frac{\pi - \angle p_2 p_1 p_3}{2\pi}.$$

For $(N, u_{\{2,3,5\}}, p)$, player 1 is not pivotal in any coalition and hence $\Phi_1(N, u_{\{2,3,5\}}, p) = 0$. Notice also that $\Phi_1(N, u_{\{1,3\}}, p) = 1/2$, since in this case 1 is pivotal at issues pointing in one half-space (Figure 1). If the other indices are calculated similarly, $\Phi_1(N, v, p) = 0.56$, $\Phi_2(N, v, p) = 0.24$, $\Phi_3(N, v, p) = 0$, $\Phi_4(N, v, p) = 0.20$ and $\Phi_5(N, v, p) = 0$.

We can see that PSE now has a power of 0.20, which is greater than the power of PP. EAJ/PNV has the largest power, 0.56. Both EP and PP are powerless, but note that neither EP nor PP is a dummy player for the spatial majority game. Indeed, EP (3) is pivotal in $\{1, 3, 4\}$, for example, since this coalition changes from a winning coalition to a losing one without 3, and $p_3 \notin co(p_{\{1,4\}})$. The same happens to PP (5): 5 is pivotal in $\{1, 4, 5\}$, for example, and $p_5 \notin co(p_{\{1,4\}})$. The 2-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index of both EP and PP is zero, because neither of them is pivotal at any issue $r \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

Now take the three variables and denote the constellation in the three-dimensional space also by p (Figure 12). The Owen-Shapley spatial power index of a party can be split as before by Lemma 1. As above, in all cases it holds $S(p) = S$. Notice that $Ad(1, p_N) = \{2, 3, 5\}$, $Ad(2, p_N) = \{1, 3, 4, 5\}$, $Ad(3, p_N) = \{1, 2, 4, 5\}$, $Ad(4, p_N) = \{2, 3, 5\}$ and $Ad(5, p_N) = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$.

Fig. 12

Observe for example that by (2), taking into account that $Ad(3, p_{\{1,2,3,4\}}) = \{1, 2, 4\}$,

$$\Phi_3(N, u_{\{1,2,3,4\}}, p) = \frac{2\pi - \angle p_1 p_3 p_2 - \angle p_1 p_3 p_4 - \angle p_2 p_3 p_4}{4\pi},$$

where the numerator represents the area of a spherical triangle (Figure 5), and since $Ad(3, p_N) = \{1, 2, 4, 5\}$,

$$\Phi_3(N, u_N, p) = \frac{2\pi - \angle p_1 p_3 p_2 - \angle p_2 p_3 p_4 - \angle p_4 p_3 p_5 - \angle p_1 p_3 p_5}{4\pi},$$

where the numerator represents the area of a spherical polygon of four sides.

If $|S| = 3$, for example, to calculate $\Phi_3(N, u_{\{1,2,3\}}, p)$, we get the results as shown in Figure 4, and the issues r to take into account determine a lune, yielding

$$\Phi_3(N, u_{\{1,2,3\}}, p) = \frac{\pi - \angle p_1 p_3 p_2}{2\pi}.$$

If $|S| = 2$, for example, to get $\Phi_3(N, u_{\{1,3\}}, p)$, we are as in Figure 3, and the index is $1/2$. Calculating the other indices similarly, $\Phi_1(N, v, p) = 0.40$, $\Phi_2(N, v, p) = 0.34$, $\Phi_3(N, v, p) = 0.07$, $\Phi_4(N, v, p) = 0.19$ and $\Phi_5(N, v, p) = 0$.

If we write the results in a table, we get:

*	EAJ/PNV (1)	EHB (2)	EP (3)	PSE (4)	PP (5)
2D	0.56	0.24	0	0.20	0
3D	0.40	0.34	0.07	0.19	0

So, if we move from the 2-dimensional model to the 3-dimensional one, our results vary from having two powerless participants to just one, which, in our opinion, is what happens in the real world. In the Basque Parliament, EP has been the key in some of the really important votes during the years of the legislature, such as the vote to pass the annual budget. Consequently, it is not a powerless party and the 3-dimensional results reflect that.

PP, however, is a long way from the other four parties in terms of their political views, which makes it quite difficult to reach an agreement with them to pass a vote. In both cases, PP is reflected as a powerless player.

Also note that, as in the 2-dimensional model, EP and PP are not dummy players in the 3-dimensional one: both parties ($i = 3, 5$) are pivotal in a coalition S for which $p_i \notin co(p_{S \setminus \{i\}})$. When the 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index is considered, PP continues being non-pivotal at any issue r , and therefore, it is powerless. However, EP changes to being pivotal for some issues, and therefore, has non-zero power.

Another interesting result is the decrease in the power of the main party, PNV. The power of PNV has decreased because with three variables its position is not so “central” with respect to the other parties. Consequently, PNV will be pivotal less times at issues r . The power of the governing party (PNV) reduced from 0.56 to 0.40 but, along with the PSE, which has nearly the same power, they are the parties with the main power. On the contrary, the power of EHB, the main opposition party, has increased. This party now is less “far” from the others, and therefore, it will be pivotal more times at issues r , which leads to an increase in power. These results also better reflect the real-world situation in the Basque Parliament. PNV has lost some votes in the legislature. These votes were mainly in relation to education and social protection. EHB, EP and PSE, which are left wing or center-left parties, joined in those votes, which resulted in the more conservative PNV party losing the vote.

6 Concluding remarks

In this paper we have studied the Owen-Shapley spatial power index for more than two dimensions. Although this index was introduced by Shapley to capture different kinds of affinities, there was not yet an explicit formula to calculate this spatial power index for more than two dimensions. In this paper, through spherical geometry tools, we have obtained a formula for unanimity games when there are three dimensions. This formula makes it possible to calculate the Owen-Shapley spatial power index for any spatial game in the three-dimensional case, employing linear combinations of indices of unanimity games. As future work, it would be interesting to get a formula for the m -dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index of unanimity games, for any m . This m -dimensional formula could also allow us to extend the result obtained by Owen and Shapley (1989) to higher dimensions, when they proved that in two-dimension space the strong point and the center of power coincide, and they leave the extension as a final open question.

In addition to the formula, we have also obtained a characterization of the Owen-Shapley spatial power index for three dimensions by means of five axioms. Reflections with respect to planes and the definition of a player’s scope have been central to characterize this spatial power index. Another future research could address the gener-

alization of the concept of scope when players are located in \mathbb{R}^m , for any m . We wonder if reflections with respect to hyperplanes might be enough to characterize the m -dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power.

We have also applied the 3-dimensional Owen-Shapley spatial power index to calculate power in the Basque Parliament. Compared to the 2-dimensional model, the presence of three variables allows us to get a richer description of the ideological attributes of the political parties, and, therefore, results which better reflect the real-world situation in this parliament. Instead of having two powerless parties, there is only one in the 3-dimensional model. The high level of power that the governing party had decreases, while the power of the main opposition party increases. The measurement of power in other parliaments could also be improved by considering more than two variables that describe the political views of their participants.

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Fig. 13

7 Appendix

Proof of Lemma 5. By 3DPI, without a loss of generality, we can suppose that $\angle aed = \angle aec = \pi/2$ (fixing e , and moving c and d towards or outwards a). By DP and 3DPI, we have to prove

$$\begin{aligned} & \varphi_0(\{0, 1, 2, 3\}, u_{\{0,1,2,3\}}, p_{\{0,1,2,3\}}) \\ &= \varphi_0(\{0, 1, 2, 3\}, u_{\{0,1,2,3\}}, q_{\{0,1,2,3\}}) + \varphi_0(\{0, 1, 2, 3\}, u_{\{0,1,2,3\}}, s_{\{0,1,2,3\}}) - \frac{1}{4}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $d' = d + (b - a)$, $e' = e + (b - a)$ and $c' = c + (b - a)$ (Figure 13). Consider $\tilde{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ and $\tilde{p}, \tilde{q}, \tilde{s} \in C^{\tilde{N}}$ such that $\tilde{p}_{\{0,1,2,3\}} = p_{\{0,1,2,3\}}$, $\tilde{q}_{\{0,1,2,3\}} = q_{\{0,1,2,3\}}$, $\tilde{s}_{\{0,1,2,3\}} = s$, $(\tilde{p}_4, \tilde{p}_5) = (c', d')$, $(\tilde{q}_4, \tilde{q}_5) = (e', d')$ and $(\tilde{s}_4, \tilde{s}_5) = (c', e')$.

By DP and 3DPI, the equality to prove is

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) + \varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}) - \frac{1}{4}. \quad (6)$$

Since φ is a power index,

$$\sum_{j=0}^5 \varphi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = 1. \quad (7)$$

By AN and RI, taking Q the plane through $a + 0.5(b - a)$ with normal vector $b - a$, equality (7) turns into

$$2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) + 2\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) + 2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = 1. \quad (8)$$

(i) We obtain another expression for $\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p})$. DP and 3DPI imply

$$\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}), \quad (9)$$

and since φ is a power index,

$$\sum_{j=0}^5 \varphi_j(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = 1.$$

Again, AN and RI, with Q the plane through $a + 0.5(b - a)$ with normal vector $(b - a)$, transform this equality into

$$2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) + 2\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) + 2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = 1.$$

Taking into account that $(\angle \tilde{q}_0 \tilde{q}_1 \tilde{q}_2, \angle \tilde{q}_0 \tilde{q}_1 \tilde{q}_4, \angle \tilde{q}_2 \tilde{q}_1 \tilde{q}_4) = (\pi/2, \pi/2, \pi/2)$, Lemma 4 implies

$$\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = \frac{1}{8},$$

and hence

$$2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = \frac{3}{4} - 2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}). \quad (10)$$

Therefore, this equality and (9) imply

$$2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \frac{3}{4} - 2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}). \quad (11)$$

(ii) We obtain another expression for $\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p})$. Similarly, by DP and 3DPI it holds

$$\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}),$$

and reasoning as in (i) we obtain

$$2\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}) = \frac{3}{4} - 2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}).$$

And hence,

$$2\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \frac{3}{4} - 2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}). \quad (12)$$

Substituting (11) and (12) in (8), equality (6) is obtained.

Finally, if $\angle cae = \angle dae$, the equality to prove is

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = 2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) - \frac{1}{4}.$$

By AN and RI, with Q the plane through e with normal vector $c - e$, we have

$$\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = \varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}),$$

which, together with (10) and (12), implies

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{q}) = \varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{s}).$$

Substituting this equality in (6), we get the result we require.

Q.E.D.

Fig. 14

Proof of Lemma 7. By 3DPI, without loss of generality, we can suppose that $\angle aed = \angle aec = \pi/2$. Let $d' = e + (e - a)$, $b' = b + 2(e - a)$, $c' = c + (b - a)$, $d' = d + (b - a)$ and $e' = e + (b - a)$ (Figure 14), and consider $\tilde{N} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$, $\tilde{p} \in C^{\tilde{N}}$ such that $\tilde{p}_{\{0,1,2,3\}} = p_{\{0,1,2,3\}}$, $(\tilde{p}_4, \tilde{p}_5, \tilde{p}_6, \tilde{p}_7) = (d', b', c', d')$, and $\tilde{q} \in C^{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1,6\}}$ such that $\tilde{p}_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1,6\}} = \tilde{q}_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1,6\}}$.

By DP and 3DPI,

$$\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_2(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}). \quad (13)$$

RI and AN imply

$$\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_3(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_4(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_5(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p})$$

and

$$\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_7(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}), \varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_6(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}),$$

and therefore, taking the definition of a power index into account,

$$2\varphi_2(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = 1 - 4\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) - 2\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}). \quad (14)$$

RI and AN imply $\varphi_2(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) = \varphi_7(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q})$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_0(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) &= \varphi_3(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) \\ &= \varphi_4(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) = \varphi_5(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}), \end{aligned}$$

and hence, taking the definition of a power index into account,

$$2\varphi_2(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) = 1 - 4\varphi_0(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}). \quad (15)$$

Substituting (14) and (15) in (13), we get:

$$-2\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) - \varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = -2\varphi_0(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}).$$

Since $\varphi_1(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) \geq 0$, then $\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) \leq \varphi_0(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q})$. By DP and 3DPI, it holds $\varphi_0(\tilde{N}, u_{\tilde{N}}, \tilde{p}) = \varphi_0(N, u_S, p)$ and $\varphi_0(\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}, u_{\tilde{N} \setminus \{1, 6\}}, \tilde{q}) = \varphi_0(N, u_S, q)$, and hence $\varphi_0(N, u_S, p) \leq \varphi_0(N, u_S, q)$. Q.E.D.